

Exploring the causes and management of Headache in Teenage children

Naveen Prabhu¹, Jayannan Jayasenan², Meyyammai Chidambaram³,
Sarala Govindarajan⁴.

1 - Assistant Professor, Department of Neurology, Meenakshi Medical College
Hospital and Research Institute, Kanchipuram, TamilNadu - 631552

2 - Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Meenakshi Medical
College Hospital and Research Institute, Kanchipuram, TamilNadu - 631552

3 - Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, Meenakshi Medical College
Hospital and Research Institute, Kanchipuram, TamilNadu - 631552

4 - Professor, Department of Neurology, Meenakshi Medical College Hospital and
Research Institute, Kanchipuram, TamilNadu - 631552

Corresponding Author - Dr.Naveen Prabhu

M.B.B.S, M.D, D.M

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION:

Headache is a prevalent issue in adolescents and poses significant impacts on their daily functioning and academic performance. This study aimed to assess headaches in terms of causes, patterns, and management among adolescents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted among 400 adolescents aged 13-19 years who presented to the pediatric outpatient department. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on the ICHD-3 diagnostic criteria, PedMIDAS scores, and VAS scales. Statistical analysis was conducted with SPSS v26 and $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS:

Of the 400 adolescents who participated, migraine was the most commonly diagnosed primary headache disorder (40%), followed by tension-type headache (30%), secondary headache (20%), and cluster/trigeminal headache (10%). Migraine was significantly more likely to occur in females compared to males (61.2%, $p < 0.001$) followed by cluster headache, which was more frequent in males than in females (75%). The most common triggers for headache were stress (81.3%), sleep deprivation (73.8%), and hormonal change (66.3%). PedMIDAS scores demonstrated that 25% of migraine patients experienced severe disability compared to 2.5% of those with secondary headaches ($p < 0.001$). Medications and behavioral therapy were primarily used for migraine and cluster headache management. In contrast, lifestyle modification was sufficient in managing tension-type headache and secondary headache ($p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSION:

Headaches in young adults, specifically migraine and cluster headaches, can lead to significant disability. Early detection, stress management, sleep hygiene, and individualized therapy are important in reducing recurrence and improving quality of life.

KEYWORDS:

Migraine, Cluster headache, Tension-type headache, Secondary headache, triggers, Pediatric Migraine Disability Assessment, International Classification of Headache Disorders

INTRODUCTION:

Headache is one of the common complaints among teenage children, which represents a serious health issue that has negative implications in their daily life and quality of life. Adolescence is a period in which there are rapid changes in growth and development, including physical, hormonal, and psychological changes that can put this age group at high risk for headache, including tension-type headache and migraine [1,2]. Headaches can impede the ability to concentrate, impact school performance and peer relations, and overall well being, often leading to missed school days and increased health care visits.

Globally, the incidence of Headache among teenagers is substantial. According to global epidemiological studies conducted among children, nearly 60% of adolescents report recurrent headaches, with migraine and tension-type headaches as the common forms [3]. In India, the prevalence of headache among teenagers attending school, is nearly 57.5% with higher incidence reported in urban areas due to lifestyle and increased academic pressure [4]. The burden of headache in adolescent age children is augmented by poor awareness, under-diagnosis and poor management of headaches, demonstrating the need for focused public health and research into headache in both developed and developing parts of the world [5].

The causes of headache have been attributed to multiple factors including biological, psychological, and environmental factors [6]. Primary headaches including migraines, are related to complex neurophysiological factors including genetic predisposition and neurovascular changes. Various triggers such as stress, sleep disturbance, dehydration, dietary issues, and hormonal changes can affect the frequency and occurrence of headaches [7]. Secondary headache disorders may stem from underlying medical issues, such as sinus infection, vision problems, or post-injury. Psychosocial factors, including anxiety, depression, and family factors also play a role in manifestation and chronicity of headaches in adolescents [8].

The management of headache needs a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach adapted to the person's headache type, severity, and lifestyle. Non-pharmacological strategies like lifestyle changes including regular sleep, hydration, healthy diet, stress management, and exercise are foundational[9]. Drug treatment, if used, should be done with a great caution in the choice of analgesics and preventive drugs and side effects need to be monitored. Behavioral interventions like cognitive-

behavioral therapy, biofeedback, and relaxation techniques have shown effectiveness in alleviating headache frequency and associated disability[10]. It is very important to educate the families and teenagers about the headache triggers and adherence to the treatment plan for the management is essential for the long term management.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the underlying causes, contributing factors, and current management approaches of headaches in our clinical population of adolescent children. We assess demographics, headache patterns, triggers, and treatment results in order to find gaps in diagnosis and treatment and provide evidence-based suggestions to raise the standard of care for adolescents who experience headaches. The objective of this study is to raise awareness, encourage early intervention, and maximize multidisciplinary management strategies for this common and frequently crippling illness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Population:

A total of 400 teenaged children, aged 13 to 19 years were included in this study from the outpatient department of Pediatrics, in a rural hospital in South India

Study Design:

This was a cross-sectional observational study conducted over a period of 12 months from November 2024 to October 2025.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged between 13 and 19 years.
- Willing to give informed consent (assent from minors and consent from parents/guardians)
- Diagnosed with primary headache disorders or exhibiting recurrent headache complaints.

Exclusion Criteria:

- History of neurological disorders other than primary headache
- Recent head trauma within the previous 3 months
- Headache secondary to systemic illness

Assessment Tools:

- Headache classification was done using the International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd edition (ICHD-3) criteria [11].
- Headache impact and disability were measured with the Pediatric Migraine Disability Assessment Scale (PedMIDAS) [12].
- Pain severity was recorded using Visual Analog Scale (VAS).

Procedure:

Eligible participants underwent a thorough clinical evaluation including history and physical assessment in order to classify the headache types according to ICHD - 3 criteria. Demographical details, characteristics of headache(frequency, intensity and duration), factors triggering the headache and the impact on school and daily activities were recorded. Data were obtained using structured questionnaire which were administered by trained clinicians. Laboratory tests and neuro-imaging were performed to rule out secondary causes.

Statistical Analysis:

The data analysis was conducted using the SPSS software version 26 (IBM Corp., USA). Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Chi-square tests/Fisher's exact test analysis were performed to compare the categorical data. Independent t-test or ANOVA analyzed continuous variables between groups. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Logistic regression was used to identify predictors of headache severity and disability.

RESULTS:

Variable	Group A (Migraine) (n=160)	Group B (Tension-type) (n=120)	Group C (Cluster/Trigeminal) (n=40)	Group D (Secondary/Miscellaneous) (n=80)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	15.3 ± 1.8	15.0 ± 1.7	15.2 ± 1.5	15.1 ± 1.9	0.789
Male (%)	62 (38.8%)	72 (60%)	30 (75%)	24 (30%)	<0.001*
Female (%)	98 (61.2%)	48 (40%)	10 (25%)	56 (70%)	

Urban Residence (%)	120 (75%)	84 (70%)	28 (70%)	56 (70%)	0.816
School Attendance (%)	154 (96.3%)	115 (95.8%)	37 (92.5%)	78 (97.5%)	0.523

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants (n = 400)

Table 1 illustrates the demographic distribution of the study population. Gender variations were highly significant with p-value <0.001 with migraine common in females and cluster headaches in males.

Variable	Group A (Migraine)	Group B (Tension-type)	Group C (Cluster/Trigeminal)	Group D (Secondary)	p-value
Headache Frequency (days/month)	8.6 ± 3.3	6.4 ± 2.9	14.2 ± 4.1	5.8 ± 2.1	<0.001*
Average Duration (hours)	7.7 ± 2.7	4.0 ± 2.3	1.5 ± 0.9	3.5 ± 2.5	<0.001*
Severe Intensity (VAS > 7)(%)	115 (71.9%)	53 (44.2%)	38 (95%)	18 (22.5%)	<0.001*

Table 2: Headache frequency and duration across groups

Table 2 demonstrates the frequency, duration and Intensity of headaches among groups with differing temporal patterns (p-value < 0.05). Group C had the highest frequency of ~14 days/month and shorter duration of ~ 1.5 hours with 95% reporting severe pain.

Trigger	Group A (%)	Group B (%)	Group C (%)	Group D (%)	p-value
Stress	130 (81.3%)	85 (70.8%)	12 (30%)	40 (50%)	<0.001*
Lack of Sleep	118 (73.8%)	70 (58.3%)	15 (37.5%)	28 (35%)	<0.001*
Hormonal Changes (Females only)	65/98 (66.3%)	20/48 (41.7%)	3/10 (30%)	35/56 (62.5%)	0.004*
Sinus Symptoms	15 (9.4%)	20 (16.7%)	2 (5%)	50 (62.5%)	<0.001*
Screen Time (>3 hours daily)	82 (51.3%)	45 (37.5%)	20 (50%)	12 (15%)	0.002*

Table 3: Prevalence of Headache triggers

Table 3 indicates the common triggers which is responsible for headache. Stress and lack of sleep were the most common trigger seen in Group A and Group B with high significance rate of $p < 0.001$. Sinus symptoms were predominantly seen in Group D (p -value < 0.001) and screen time for more than 3 hours affected the Group C category (p -value < 0.002).

Disability Level	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	p-value
No/Mild (<10)	35 (21.9%)	65 (54.2%)	10 (25%)	62 (77.5%)	<0.001*
Moderate (11-30)	85 (53.1%)	40 (33.3%)	20 (50%)	16 (20%)	
Severe (>30)	40 (25%)	15 (12.5%)	10 (25%)	2 (2.5%)	

Table 4: PedMIDAS Scores by Headache Type

Table 4 reveals the headache related disability measured using PedMIDAS Scale. Migraine and Cluster headache groups showed higher PedMIDAS severity compared to Tension type and secondary headache group with p -value < 0.001 . Secondary headache showed predominantly mild or no disability

Treatment Modality	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	p-value
Lifestyle modification only	50 (31.3%)	67 (55.8%)	10 (25%)	65 (81.3%)	<0.001*
Pharmacological treatment	110 (68.8%)	53 (44.2%)	30 (75%)	15 (18.7%)	
Behavioral therapy	65 (40.6%)	20 (16.7%)	15 (37.5%)	10 (12.5%)	0.002*
Clinical improvement at 3 months	123 (76.9%)	95 (79.2%)	27 (67.5%)	70 (87.5%)	0.082

Table 5: Treatment Patterns and Improvement by Headache types

Table 5 illustrates the distribution of treatment strategies and the patient outcomes. Pharmacotherapy and Behavioral therapy were commonly used in the migraine and cluster headache groups. Secondary headaches were managed with the lifestyle modifications alone (p-value < 0.001). Improvement rates were high across all the groups.

DISCUSSION:

The average age of the participants in our study was found to be 15.2 ± 1.7 years, which supports that mid-adolescence represents the most vulnerable time for headache occurrence. There was a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$) in gender. Migraines and secondary headaches predominated in females (61.2% and 70%), whereas males predominated in tension-type and cluster headaches (60% and 75%). Urban adolescents made up about three-fourths of the study population suggesting uniform exposure across residential backgrounds. School attendance was high in all the groups with >92% and no statistical difference was observed ($p = 0.523$). Similarly, in the study conducted by Talebian et al.[13], the average age of children suffering from headache was 8.88 ± 2.74 years, which was not significantly different for males and females ($P = 0.27$). In the same way, there was no significant difference between the mean ages of migraine (9.25 ± 2.72 years) and tension-type headache (8.51 ± 2.68 years) ($P = 0.181$). Thus, both the studies did not show any significance in mean age across headache types.

The cluster/trigeminal group had the highest frequency of headaches (14.2 ± 4.1 days/month), followed by migraine (8.6 ± 3.3), tension-type (6.4 ± 2.9), and secondary headaches (5.8 ± 2.1) ($p < 0.001$). The duration was longest for migraine (7.7 ± 2.7 hours) and shortest for cluster/trigeminal (1.5 ± 0.9 hours) ($p < 0.001$). Severe pain intensity was observed using the VAS Scale (>7) where cluster/trigeminal had severe pain (95%), followed by migraine (71.9%), tension-type (44.2%), and secondary (22.5%) headaches ($p < 0.001$). Overall, our results demonstrated significant differences in frequency, duration, and severity among the groups, with cluster headaches being the most severe headache overall. According to the systematic review conducted by Abu-Arafeh et al. [14], the median prevalence of all headache types in the school-aged population was 58.4%, while the prevalence of migraine was 7.7%. Both the studies supports the idea that headache disorders are common in school-aged and adolescent populations, which highlights the importance of early diagnosis and management.

In this study, Stress was the most common trigger for headache affecting 81.3% of migraine patients and 70.8% of tension-type headache patients. This was significantly higher than the 30% of cluster/trigeminal headache patients, and the 50% of secondary headache patients ($p < 0.001$). Sleep deprivation was also a notable trigger, being reported by 73.8% of migraine patients and 58.3% of tension-type headache patients ($p < 0.001$). In women especially, hormonal triggers were significant in migraine (66.3%) compared to tension-type (41.7%) and cluster/trigeminal headache (30%) patients ($p = 0.004$). Sinus symptoms were reported more frequently in secondary headaches (62.5%), and long screen time (>3 hrs) was frequently reported in migraine (51.3%) and cluster/trigeminal headache (50%) groups ($p = 0.002$). Our results closely aligns with the study conducted by Kemper KJ et al [15] where they found that the stress was the most frequently reported trigger among adolescents (86%), followed by fatigue (55%), weather changes (48%) and dehydration (48%).

There was also a significant difference in headache-related disability across the groups ($p < 0.001$). Moderate to severe disability was mostly seen in migraine (78.1%) and cluster/trigeminal headache patients (75%), and mild disability predominated with tension-type headache (54.2%) patients, and secondary headache (77.5%) patients. In contrast, the study by Kröner-Herwig et al. [16], revealed that

81.2% of children experienced no or low disability, whereas only 1.4% had severe disability.

The approach to management also differed significantly across the groups ($p < 0.001$). The pharmacological approach to management was significantly more likely to be required at follow up in migraine (68.8%) and cluster/trigeminal headache (75%) patients, whereas the management of secondary headaches (81.3%) and tension-type (55.8%) headache patients was generally reliant on lifestyle modification alone. And finally, behavioral therapy was employed more frequently in migraine (40.6%) cases ($p = 0.002$). Clinical improvement at the follow up of three months was found to occur in most patients in all three groups—76.9% in migraine. Similar management patterns were noted in the study by Kemper KJ et al [15], where half of the adolescents engaged in relaxation techniques to help alleviate the symptoms. These ranged from going to bed (83%) to listening to music (69%) and watching television (55%). In terms of medical management, 76% of participants stated they used a prescription medication and 59% reported using dietary supplements. Among those dietary supplements, participants reported using a multivitamin (33%), magnesium (28%), and riboflavin (10%).

CONCLUSION:

This study findings indicate that headaches are prevalent among mid-adolescents, with the most severe forms being cluster headaches and migraines. The predominant triggers for headaches included stress, sleep deficiency and hormonal shifts, particularly among females. There was variation related to headache type for management needs- pharmacologic and behavioral based interventions were more commonly needed for migraine and cluster headaches while changes in lifestyle were sufficient for tension-type and secondary headaches. Early recognition and tailored management is important to reduce the headache burden in adolescents.

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